

Listado de Publicaciones Científicas Usando la Metodología KID

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82. Norma Flores-Holguín, Juan Frau, and [Daniel Glossman-Mitnik](#), “Exploring the Reactivity Landscape of Bioactive Peptides Using Conceptual DFT and Molecular Modelling Tools”, *Computational Biology and Chemistry* **119**, 108571 (2025).
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80. Norma Flores-Holguín, Juan Frau, and [Daniel Glossman-Mitnik](#), “Exploring the Chemical and Pharmaceutical Potential of Kapakahines A-G Using Conceptual Density Functional Theory-Based Computational Peptidology”, *Computation* **13** (5), 111 (2025).
79. Norma Flores-Holguín, Joan S. Salas-Leiva, Erick J. Núñez-Vázquez, Dariel Tovar-Ramírez, and [Daniel Glossman-Mitnik](#), “Marine Toxins as Pharmaceutical Treasure Troves: A Focus on Saxitoxin Derivatives from a Computational Point of View”, *Molecules* **29**, 275 (2024).
78. Norma Flores-Holguín, Juan Frau and [Daniel Glossman-Mitnik](#), “Investigating the Chemical Reactivity of Kahalalides: A Promising Source of Therapeutic Peptides from Marine Natural Products Using Conceptual Density Functional Theory”, *ChemistrySelect* **8** (42), e202303207 (2023).
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71. Smitha S Bhat, Sushma Pradeep, Sharanagouda S Patil, Norma Flores-Holguín, [Daniel Glossman-Mitnik](#), Juan Frau, Sarana Rose Sommano, Nemat Ali, Mohamed Mohany, Chandan Shivamallu, Shashanka K Prasad, Shiva Prasad Kollur, “Preliminary Evaluation of Lablab purpureus Phytochemicals for Anti-BoHV-1 Activity Using In Vitro and In Silico Approaches”, *ACS Omega* **8**, 22684-22697 (2023).
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